

Language, Technology and Empowerment

Anamika Shukla¹ & Chitresh Soni²

1. Associate Professor 'English', School of Humanities, IGNOU, New Delhi
2. Assistant Professor, School of Translation Studies & Training, IGNOU, New Delhi

Received : 03/06/2023

1st BPR : 09/06/2023

2nd BPR : 16/06/2023

Accepted : 21/06/2023

Abstract

Abstract: The heritage texts of Sanskrit and Indian languages contain knowledge helpful for wellbeing of humanity. The onus is on scholars of these traditions to put forth the huge ambit of this knowledge in a succinct and articulate manner to the masses. Knowledge is for one and all. The shrunk coverage attached with the texts particularly the access to the university classroom as well as good teachers is a hindrance in the path of inclusivity and nation building. This paper delves upon our vast intellectual heritage and the means to inculcate its noesis in the acumen of the young and not so young alike. While highlighting the best practices we shall also propound effective models to disseminate this knowledge for linguistic and technological empowerment of learners.

Key words: Language, Technology & Empowerment.

1.1 Introduction:

Continuous intellectual endeavour has been the mark of Indian civilization. Rishis have focussed their minds onto various disciplines or rather the various discipline of knowledge and schools of thought are the result of their constant endeavour to bring out the best nature and cosmos has to offer to us. This churning resulted in fantastic texts of health science i.e., Ayurveda, mind-body regulators such as Yoga and unifying theory of the cosmos i.e., Vedanta. India that is Bharat has been Vīśvaguru owing to the penances of these great men. In the mean-time the tradition became static due to factors external and internal. The flow was restricted but it never dried up.

This flow needs to be taken forward through tremendous technological progress made in the 20th Century. India is a metaverse of languages with twenty-two languages in the eighth schedule of constitution (Article 344 (1) and 35). Namely -

- Assamese
- Dogri
- Kannada
- Malayalam
- Maithili
- Punjabi
- Sindhi
- Urdu
- Bengali
- Gujarati
- Kashmiri
- Manipuri
- Nepali
- Sanskrit
- Tamil
- Bodo
- Hindi
- Konkani
- Marathi
- Oriya
- Santhali
- Telugu

These languages belong to four language families, Indo-Aryan, Dravidian, Austro-Asiatic and Tibeto-Burman (Baldrige 96). Other than these, 100 un-scheduled languages are reported in the 2001 census. The Govt. of India, state govts and local bodies must put their act together to create resources to encash linguistic dividend. India resides in villages and they speak their vernaculars, dialects and sub-dialects. Educational resources based upon the Indian Knowledge Tradition should reach them. The best way to move forward in this direction is through the conjunction of Indian Languages and language resources. Only through this India can be the flagbearer of Educational Revolution 4.0 (propounded by

Sir Anthony Seldon). A great deal of groundwork has been done by the GoI and its agencies to prepare for the challenges of the 21st century. We shall be presenting these efforts in this paper as well as the modern-day compulsions of technology, dynamic change in the educational environment due to Covid-19 pandemic and the plethora of opportunities opening up due to the demographic dividend India has due to its young generation. NEP-2020 envisions to transform India by translating these possibilities into reality.

1.2 Digital Divide: Digital divide consists of many aspects, it is the lack of access devices, poor network infrastructure to access the content and not having the skills to access and navigate the systems, services, repositories and contents. This digital divide came into vogue discussion especially during the Covid-19 period when many students enrolled in universities in metro cities were forced to leave the classrooms and while residing in the remote areas in the lockdown period, they had to face great deal of difficulties in coping up with online studies going on with their respective institutions. The NEP and the initiatives of the MoE, Govt of India are directed towards addressing the same issue.

1.3 Pedagogy and Technology

One thing needs to be very clear in the minds of head of HEIs and faculty that technology isn't teaching-learning in itself. It is an empowering phenomenon which brings whole lot of Ideas together, bridges the distance gap for learners situated in hinterlands, enhances the reach of expert faculty across length and breadth of the country and provides access above all. The SWAYAM PRABHA TV channels are an excellent initiative in this regard. The SWAYAM PRABHA is a group of 34 DTH channels devoted to telecasting of high-quality educational programmes on 24X7 basis using the GSAT-15 satellite. This initiative is providing access to millions of aspirational learners in rural and urban areas. Every day, new content is made available for at least (4) hours which would be repeated 5 more times in a day, allowing the students to choose the time of their convenience. The channels are uplinked from BISAG-N, Gandhinagar. The contents are provided by NPTEL, IITs, UGC, CEC, IGNOU. The INFLIBNET Centre maintains the web portal. Likewise, the SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspirational Minds) portal of the MoE, which primarily has the goals of access, equity and quality has been proving itself a worthy addition to modern day educational environment. Consisting of four quadrants namely e-content, videos, discussion forum (DF) and assessment; the objective of this effort is to take the best teaching learning resources to all, including the most disadvantaged. SWAYAM seeks to bridge the digital divide for students who have hitherto remained untouched by the digital revolution and have not been able to join the mainstream of the knowledge economy. In the current framework up to 40 percent of credits can be carried forward to award of a degree from a conventional or open distance system of education.

1.4 Policy Initiatives

The Digital India (DI) initiative of Govt of India, considering technology as a leveller and springboard, aims to make India as a just and equitable society through technology. This knowledge society will be the backbone of "Aatmanirbhar Bharat". Intent, Inclusion, Investment, Infrastructure and Innovation are the basic principles and factors which will play a major role in this. Digital India also aims to develop and disseminate tech-based resources with Speed, Simplicity and Service. Taking cue from the DI The National Education Policy-2020 envisions to make our nation a knowledge economy. India can become a global superpower only if advancements are achieved in fundamental sciences, cutting edge technologies and state of the art AI systems. India is a linguistic area (Emeneau 1956) and multilingualism, language technology, e-learning, multimedia and lastly Artificial Intelligence (AI) are the current and future technologies to reckon with. Two brilliant concept papers named AIRAWAT and Responsible AI have been prepared by the NITI Aayog on it.

Major Initiatives

1.4.1 TDIL:

Knowledge of English is limited to a very small section of the population in the country. The rest often cannot access or comprehend digital resources which are available mainly in English.

Technology Development for Indian Languages (TDIL) programme has been initiated by the DeitY for developing information processing tools and techniques to facilitate human-computer interaction (read intelligent) without language barriers. It also aims to create and provide access to multilingual knowledge resources, and integrate them to develop innovative user products and services. TDIL has its active participation in international and national standardization bodies such as ISO, UNICODE, World-wide-Web consortium (W3C) and Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) in the area of language technology standardization. This ensures adequate representation of Indian languages in existing and future language technology standards.

The Localization Projects Management Framework (LPMF) has also been initiated by DeitY to help localize applications under the MMPs and other government applications. DeitY is also formulating a new mission mode project named as e-Bhasha to help develop and disseminate digital content in local languages to India's largely non-English speaking population. The disabled friendly content and systems are being developed as per accessibility standards.

1.4.2 Central Institute of Indian Languages (CIIL): CIIL was established by the the MoE (then MHRD) to promote and coordinate the development of Indian languages and bring about the essential unity of India Languages through scientific studies, interdisciplinary research, mutual enrichment of languages; and thus, contribute towards the emotional integration of people of India.

The aims and objectives of CIIL are (official website)

- Advices and Assists Central as well as State Governments in the matters of language.
- Contributes to the development of all Indian Languages by creating content and corpus.
- Protects and Documents Minor, Minority and Tribal Languages.
- Promotes Linguistic harmony by teaching 20 Indian languages to non-native learners.

The National Translation Mission, National Testing Services, Linguistic Data Consortium (LDC-IL), Classical Languages cell are the various organs of CIIL. The Bharatvaani portal, Bhasha-Bharati and Katha Bharati are its current and future initiatives.

1.4.3 Indian Language Corpora Initiative:

The Indian Language Corpora Initiative is Department of Information Technology (DIT), Govt of India funded project to develop parallel annotated corpora in 11 Indian Languages in the health and tourism domain. These include 8 Indo-Aryan languages (Hindi, Gujarati, Marathi, Bangla, Oriya, Konkani, Punjabi and Urdu), 3 Dravidian languages (Tamil, Telugu, Malayalam) and English as well. It also aims to create standards for these languages. It was a consortia project with Prof. Girish Nath Jha at JNU, New Delhi as its consortium leader.

Major aims of the project are:

- Corpora collection
- Corpora annotation
- Draft Standards
- Tools Development

1.4.5 National Mission on Education through ICT:

The NMEICT has been envisaged as a Centrally Sponsored Scheme to leverage the potential of ICT, in teaching and learning process for the benefit of all the learners in Higher Education Institutions in anytime anywhere mode. During the XI five-year plan period its goal was to increase the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in Higher Education by 5 percentage points. On the basis of the three golden

principles of access, equity and quality it also aims to provide high quality content and low-cost access-cum computing devices (with no costs incurred on the part of students) to all the learners in the country.

The mission has two major components:

- Providing connectivity, along with the provision for access devices, to institutions and learners;
- Content generation

The SWAYAM, SWAYAM PRABHA, Virtual Labs, e-yantra, FOSSE and NDLI are part of the NMEICT framework.

1.4.5.1 National Digital Library of India:

The NDLI under the aegis of NMEICT and funded by the Department of Higher Education, MoE, Govt of India is a large online archive of 35 million titles in 10 languages and more than 25 lakh active users. In addition to being a virtual repository of Books and other content through a single window system it also hosts modules for 'Test Preparation' (JEE, NEET, GATE, NET and CBSE exams), Study at home, Covid19 research repository and career development and recruitment. It has been developed for the public by Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur. It has been cross linked with other tech initiatives like Shodhganga of the INFLIBNET to provide dynamic content access to the learners. It has learning material for possibly every role of the learner right from the school level to the life-long learner. The place where it needs to improve is that the search results are not sometimes relevant to the learner. It has filters for content search but it doesn't provide advanced search results. In the opinion of authors', the administrators should come out with better algorithms to suit the nature of query of the learners e.g. It should have the option to differentiate between a thesis and a research paper and a book and a monograph. It provides access but the search results should be smart enough.

1.4.5.2 Indian Research Information Network System (IRINS):

Under the aegis of NMEICT it has been developed by the INFLIBNET centre as a web-based Research and Information Management (RIM) service. It has integrated with ORCID, SCOPUS ID, Research ID, Microsoft Academic ID, Google Scholar ID or the purpose of ingesting scholarly publication from various sources. The IRINS is available as free software-as-service to the academic and R&D organizations in India. IRINS facilitates the academic R&D organizations and faculty members, scientists to collect, curate and showcase the scholarly communication activities and provide an opportunity to create the scholarly network.

1.4.5.3 Shodh Shudhhi Plagiarism Detection Software (PDS): It is a plagiarism detection software which helps students and researchers in developing unique ideas, concepts and information without duplication. It helps in achieving better research outcomes by adding to the corpus of existing knowledge and thereby increases the reputation of the university or the institution.

1.5 Conclusion:

India has a distinct characteristic in terms of language diversity. It is a multilingual society where tendencies of languages shift and language assimilations are also noticed. Many hybrid creolised languages are also evolving to be used as a link language. Unlike monolingual societies, multilingual societies do not propagate or acknowledge a strict one language one nation boundary. According to census 2011 India is home to 270 mother tongues which have 10 thousand or more speakers. In this scenario the R&D scenario is not where it should have been. Policy initiatives such as NEP-2020 aim to break the status quo and deliver on the promise of access, equity and quality while envisaging the medium of education to be the mother tongue. NEP also aims to harness technology to get the best out of every single child of India. Any technological advancement should be fair, just, accountable, socially uplifting and empowering to the citizens of India in general and learners in particular. Access and equity are being maintained by various initiatives for learners but at the same time keeping multilingualism in mind, it should almost always be equitable for all the languages of India.

References:

- 1 <https://rajbhasha.gov.in/en/languages-included-eighth-schedule-indian-constitution>
- 2 http://lsi.gov.in:8081/jspui/bitstream/123456789/64/1/37632_2001_LAN.pdf (pp. 7-8)
- 3 <https://swayamprabha.gov.in/>
- 4 <https://swayamprabha.gov.in/>
- 5 <https://swayam.gov.in/about>
- 6 <http://tdil.meity.gov.in/>
- 7 <http://tdil.meity.gov.in/>
- 8 <http://ciil.org/>
- 9 <http://ciil.org/>
- 10 <http://Inflibnet.ac.in/>

